

Thermal Analysis of Fe(II), Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) Chelates of 2'-Hydroxy-4-Methoxy-5'-Methylchalkone Oxime

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The thermal analysis of Fe(II), Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) chelates of 2'-hydroxy-4-methoxy-5'-methylchalkone oxime (HMMCO) was studied by TG and DTA techniques. All chelates show somewhat similar TG and DTA profiles when heated in an atmosphere of air. A sharp exothermic peak in the range 150-200° was observed preceded to endothermic peak for dehydration of metal chelate. This sharp exothermic peak may be caused due to the transition from unstable state to stable state of the chelate. Broad exothermic peak was observed above 300°, corresponding to rapid mass-loss in TG curve, which may be due to oxidation-reduction reactions. A relative thermal stability of metal chelates is reported.

VERY few systems are reported showing the relationship between thermal stability of metal chelates and structure of chelating agents¹. Wendlandt²⁻⁵ and Hill^{6,7}, studied the thermal properties of metal chelates with various chelating ligands. Seshagiri *et al*⁸, Sheshadri⁹ and other workers¹⁰⁻¹² reported the thermal stability of metal chelates of oxime. HMMCO¹³ readily form chelates with transition metal ions¹⁴. The purpose of this study is to report thermal stability of the metal chelates. The techniques employed are thermogravimetry (TG) and differential thermal analysis (DTA).

Materials and Methods :

Preparation of Metal Chelates :

Metal chelates of HMMCO were synthesized as reported earlier¹⁴.

Thermoanalytical Techniques :

TG and DTA studies were performed in the Chemistry Department of Indian Institute of Technology, Powai, Bombay (India). A brief account of TG and DTA apparatus is given below :

Thermogravimetric Analysis : The thermal balance consists of phosphor-bronze spring; the contraction of the spring due to mass-loss was converted into electrical signals by means of a LVDT which was then amplified and fed to the recorder.

The sample holder consisted of a light platinum basket. A vertical furnace was employed for heating the sample. The sample holder was surrounded in the constant temperature zone of the furnace. Heating rate was adjusted to 5-6°/min

manually. A precalibrated chromelalumel thermocouple was placed very near to the sample holder to measure the temperature. About 40-50 mg of the sample was used for each run.

Differential Thermal Analysis : The emf of the differential thermocouple was fed to a recording potentiometer.

The following conditions were maintained in all the experiments.

- Reference material : Al₂O₃ (Calcined at 1200°)
- Heating Rate : 7-8°/min.
- Sample holders : Platinum cups.
- Weight of the sample : Nearly 50 mg.

Results and Discussion

Mass-loss Study :

The mass-loss curves of the metal chelates are shown in Fig. 1. The thermal dissociation data, including initial decomposition temperature (Ta), inflexion point temperature (Tb) and per cent-mass-loss (%W) due to the oxidation-reduction reactions¹⁷ are incorporated in Table 1.

Fe(II)(HMMCO)₂.5H₂O :

The mass-loss curve of Fe(II) (HMMCO)₂.5H₂O is shown as curve A in Fig. 1. It can be seen that the dehydration of the Fe(II)(HMMCO)₂.5H₂O takes place between 100° and 200° (12.50% found, 11.39% ther.) as one step process. A corresponding weight loss in this range suggests the association of five water molecules with the chelate. Above 200° the

Fig. 1. TG curves, (A) Fe(II)(HMMCO)₃.5H₂O, (B) Fe(III)(HMMCO)₃.6H₂O, (C) Co(II)(HMMCO)₃.3H₂O, (D) Ni(II)(HMMCO)₃.2H₂O, (E) Cu(II)(HMMCO)₃.3H₂O.

TABLE 1—THERMAL STABILITY DATA OF METAL CHELATES

Chelates	Ta°(C)	Tb°(C)	%W
Fe(II)(HMMCO) ₃ .5H ₂ O	300	540	73
Fe(III)(HMMCO) ₃ .6H ₂ O	240	530	77
Co(II)(HMMCO) ₃ .3H ₂ O	390	540	73
Ni(II)(HMMCO) ₃ .2H ₂ O	260	690	80
Cu(II)(HMMCO) ₃ .3H ₂ O	240	680	82

Ta, Temperature of initial decomposition without considering dehydration.

Tb, Temperature at inflection point of oxidation-reduction reaction.

%W, Calculated from mass-loss curve considering only anhydrous chelate

TG curve shows gradual mass loss upto 350° beyond which abrupt mass loss has been observed which indicates oxidation-reduction reaction¹⁷.

Fe(III)(HMMCO)₃.6H₂O :

The mass-loss curve of this metal chelate is shown as curve B in Fig. 1. Fe(III)(HMMCO)₃.6H₂O indicates the evolution of six water molecules

in temperature range 130 to 200° (11.00% found, 10.70% ther.). Further decomposition takes place above 300°.

Co(HMMCO)₃.3H₂O :

The mass-loss curve of this chelate is given in Fig. 1 (Curve C). Co(HMMCO)₃.3H₂O dehydrates between 100 and 250° (8.50% found, 7.97% ther.) and after dehydration this chelate has been observed to be stable upto 390°. Then TG curve shows rapid mass-loss which may be caused due to oxidation-reduction reactions.

Ni(HMMCO)₃.2H₂O :

The mass-loss curve of this chelate is shown as curve D in Fig. 1. Ni(HMMCO)₃.2H₂O chelate evolved 2 moles of water of hydration per mole between 100 and 180° (6.0% found, 5.46% ther.) as one step process and further decomposition takes place above 260°. Rapid mass-loss above 260° may be caused due to the oxidation-reduction reactions.

Cu(HMMCO)₃.3H₂O :

The mass-loss curve of this chelate is given as curve E in Fig. 1. Cu(HMMCO)₃.3H₂O loses the water of hydration in the temperature range 100 to 200° and continuous mass-loss is observed upto 400°, after that rapid mass-loss is observed which can be attributed to the oxidation-reduction reactions.

In general the water of hydration may be considered either as the crystal or as co-ordination water. According to Nikolav *et al*¹⁵ water eliminating below 150° can be considered as the crystal water and water eliminatoy above 150° may be due to its coordination to the metal ion. In the present stueies it is observed that water of hydration has been eliminated between 100 and 200° which suggests the presence of water of hydration as coordinated water as well as crystal one.

In the present studies initial decomposition temperature (Ta) and inflection temperature (Tb) have been used to determine thermal stability of metal chelates. The initial decomposition temperature (Ta) is frequently used to define the relative thermal stability of metal chelates¹⁶. On the basis of experimental findings in the present course of studies and observations made by earlier workers^{8,9,19}, the relative thermal stability for HMMCO chelates can be given as

Differential Thermal Analysis :

The DTA curves of chelates are shown in Figs. 2 and 3. Small exothermic peak is observed in most of the cases below 100°, with no TG mass-loss ;

Fig. 2. DTA curves : (A) Fe(II)(HMMCO)₂.5H₂O, (B) Fe(III)(HMMCO)₂.6H₂O, (C) Co(II)(HMMCO)₂.3H₂O.

Fig. 3. DTA curves : (D) Ni(II)(HMMCO)₂.2H₂O, (E) Cu(II)(HMMCO)₂.3H₂O.

this can be interpreted in terms of isomerisation process¹⁶. Endothermic and exothermic peaks of DTA curves for almost all chelates in the temperature range 150-230° indicate dehydration and transition of unstable to stable state of chelates respectively. The appearance of sharp exothermic peaks in this temperature range has been demonstrated by earlier workers¹⁶ for the transition of one state to another. Further, all broad DTA curves are characterized by exothermic peak in the temperature range of 300 to 600° as observed in

other chelates of oxime^{8,9}. In all the cases, however, the exothermic peak was preceded by a broad endothermic peak. This behaviour can be interpreted in terms of the dissociation of the chelates followed by exothermic oxidation-reduction reactions. Such type of observation was noted by Chang and Wendlandt¹⁷ earlier. It is observed that DTA peaks temperature and mass-loss temperature on TG curve do not coincide with each other. This is probably due to the fact that separate instruments have been employed for TG and DTA studies.

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